

Regulating Wastewater Discharge and Effluent in Laguna de Bay: Issues, Challenges, and Lessons

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Abstract. Despite the existence of management and regulation in Laguna de Bay since 1966, the water quality of the lake continues to deteriorate. By mapping and examining the laws, policies, and tools employed in the last 50 years, the study reveals trends, characteristics, and changes over time; a multi-institutional regulators landscape; and the issues, challenges, and lessons of regulation. Moreover, conflicting policy frameworks, limitations of regulatory tools, and insufficient resources of regulators impede effective and efficient regulation. The study concludes that there is a weak or inadequate regulation of wastewater discharge and effluent in Laguna de Bay. Thus, it recommends a multi-pronged approach to addressing this weakness through regular review of policies; adoption of tools for adaptive change and innovation; a more collaborative and participative approach of regulation; and strengthening of regulators' financial, personnel, and technological resources for effective and efficient regulation.

Keywords: regulation, wastewater discharge, environmental governance, multi-institutional regulators

Laguna de Bay, also known as Laguna Lake, is the largest freshwater lake in the Philippines. It is a multi-use water resource system used for fisheries and aquaculture, floodwater reservoir, navigation, power generation, industrial cooling, irrigation for agriculture, and sociocultural activities. Although the lake has been managed and regulated since 1966 with a multi-institutional regulators landscape, water quality continues to deteriorate primarily due to pollution from wastewater discharge/effluent from domestic and industrial sources.

The waters of Laguna de Bay are severely polluted. In fact, the Pilot Ecosystem Account for Laguna de Bay Basin Report in 2016 by Wealth Accounting and the Valuation of Ecosystem Services (WAVES) found that 81% of biochemical oxygen demand (BOD) loading in the lake comes from households/domestic sources; 9% from industries; 5% from agriculture; 3% from solid wastes; and 2% from forests. Meanwhile, dela Peña et al. (2021) confirmed the presence of diarrhea-causing *Cryptosporidium* species in the surface waters of the lake and its tributaries due to fecal contamination. Algal blooming in Laguna de Bay also causes seasonal fish kills affecting fishermen's economy (*UPDate Online*, 2019).

Eutrophication is another problem affecting water quality in Laguna de Bay. Eutrophication is the process of excessive nutrient loading, particularly phosphorous and nitrogen, into bodies of water, resulting in oxygen depletion and causing the death of aquatic animals like fish (Cloern et al., 2006). Nutrient loading usually comes from farmlands treated with fertilizers and detergents from domestic wastewater (Global Environment Facility, 2017). Furthermore, experts described the lake's ecosystem as extremely stressed due to population explosion, industrialization, urbanization, deforestation, and uncontrolled land conversion (Baclig, 2022).

Referring to all these causes of water quality deterioration in Laguna de Bay, this article seeks to investigate how the management of Laguna de Bay has been done; and how the regulation of wastewater discharge/effluent has been implemented. The study also attempts to find out if there is a regulation weakness or inadequacy somewhere.

Management and regulation of lakes are complicated and long-term tasks. Various factors are required with utmost consideration of the environmental, sociocultural, and biological aspects. Efficient coordination of efforts between governments, communities, landowners, and individuals is also necessary. In the case of Laguna de Bay, management issues are caused by poor implementation of national and local policies (Tobias, 2017); conflicting policy frameworks of the Laguna Lake Development Authority or LLDA (Malayang, 1993); conflicts brought about by the complex institutional and organizational arrangements (Sly, 1993); and areas of conflicts among stakeholders (Santos-Borja & Nepomuceno, 2005).

Although the aforementioned studies are notable in elucidating their objectives, they presented a more general view of managing a lake. Since Laguna de Bay has many activities to regulate, this study focuses its investigation on the regulation of wastewater discharge and effluent by examining the laws and policies, the tools used, the trends, characteristics, and changes over time; the multi-institutional regulators landscape; and the issues, challenges and lessons of regulation in the last five decades, starting in 1966, when LLDA was created through the enactment of Republic Act (RA) 4850. This study attempts to answer the following questions:

- What are the laws, policies, and tools employed in regulating wastewater discharge and effluent in Laguna de Bay from 1966 to 2016? What are the trends, characteristics, and changes over time?
- Who are the regulators?
- What are the issues, challenges, and lessons of regulation?
- Inferring from the objectives, what may be recommended to improve the regulation?

Figure 1
Laguna de Bay Bounded by the Five Provinces and Metro Manila

Source. Laguna Lake Development Authority (n.d.).

Research Framework and Methodology

This study maps and analyzes the laws, policies, and tools employed by the regulators in Laguna de Bay from 1966 to 2016. As mentioned earlier, the formal management of the lake commenced when RA 4850 was enacted in 1966 creating the LLDA. This study is guided by the definition by Baldwin et al. (1998) of regulation as an authoritative promulgation of a set of rules by a public agency that, with some mechanism, monitors and promotes compliance with these rules; and the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development’s (OECD, 2002) fundamental elements of regulation. OECD posits that the implementation of regulatory policies and the usefulness of regulatory tools depend on the existence and functioning of the right set of regulatory institutions. According to OECD (2002), these three fundamental elements must be mutually supportive to each other to maximize the efficiency and

effectiveness of a regulatory agenda. Figure 2 shows the author's originally formulated diagram of the research framework of the study.

Figure 2
Research Framework

The study follows a qualitative and descriptive format, guided by Shank's (2002) definition of qualitative research as "a form of systematic empirical inquiry into meaning" (p.5). In this sense, the study content analyzes the laws and policies in regulating wastewater discharge/effluent in Laguna de Bay, such as republic acts (RAs), presidential decrees (PD), executive orders (EOs), memorandum circulars (MCs), board resolutions (BRs), and ordinances issued by local government units (LGUs); the implementing institutions/regulators; and the tools employed from 1966 up to 2016. This timeline was grouped into five decades or periods for analyses and discussions. The study also investigated the trends, characteristics, and changes of the laws/policies and tools over time.

Results and Discussions

Laws, Policies, and Tools

The Philippines' rapid population growth, urbanization, and industrialization in the last 50 years, from 1966 to 2016, resulted in environmental degradation, including water pollution in the Laguna de Bay. To address these issues, the Philippine government instituted various environmental laws and policies to ensure that the environment is protected, and that public health is given priority through a clean environment. This study examines these laws and policies, presenting the highlights, the characteristics, the trends, and changes over time.

In 1966-1976, major laws and policies were issued primarily to control or mitigate water pollution in the Philippines. These laws and policies are command-and-control in nature and approach. Among them is the Sanitation Code of the Philippines (PD 856), which updates and codifies scattered sanitation laws of the country and orders proper sewage and waste collection and disposal. The National Pollution Control Decree of 1976 (PD 984) aims to prevent, abate, and control pollution of water, air, and land in the country. The 1976 Water Code of the Philippines (PD 1067) establishes the basic principles and frameworks on the use, control, and conservation of all water resources in the country.

Pollution Mitigation in the Laguna de Bay

Republic Act 4850 enacted in 1966 created the LLDA as the primary regulatory body to protect, preserve, and develop Laguna de Bay in accordance with pollution control and environmental protection policies of the government. One of the major policies of the LLDA to mitigate pollution in the Laguna de Bay is the implementation of the Environmental Users Fee System (EUFS). The EUFS is a pioneering water pollution charging system in the country that punishes polluters, e.g., businesses and industries, using the waters of Laguna de Bay for discharging wastewater/effluent. They are required to conform to the effluent standards and guidelines issued by LLDA and the Department of Environment and Natural Resources (DENR), including payment of user fees. EUFS covers all water pollution point sources from industrial, commercial, domestic, and agricultural sectors. The goal is to reduce pollution loading in Laguna de Bay by enjoining dischargers of liquid wastes to consider the cost of environmental degradation in their business decisions and operations. Although polluters are paying the EUFS fees, the LLDA's policy of issuing cease-and-desist orders (CDOs) and notices of violations (NOVs) still applies to businesses/industries that failed the effluent standards set by DENR and LLDA. Six years after the implementation of EUFS, the LLDA claimed that the biochemical oxygen demand (BOD) loading in Laguna de Bay showed a remarkable reduction. However, as lake users increased over time and 81% of the BOD loading in the lake is from households/domestic sources, per report of the Wealth Accounting and the Valuation of Ecosystem Services (WAVES) in 2016, the LLDA faces an enormous challenge to mitigate lake pollution.

In the second decade or period (1977-1986) more laws and policies were issued to strengthen government policies on pollution control and mitigation. Hence, various government agencies and institutions amended some laws and policies, standards, codes of practice, guidelines, etc. For instance, in 1977, two major environmental laws were issued by the Office of the President: PD 1151, known as the Philippine Environmental Policy, and PD 1152, known as the Philippine Environmental Code. PD 1151 aims to protect the rights of the people to a healthy environment through environmental impact assessments and statements (EIS), while PD 1152 focuses on achieving and maintaining air quality levels, protecting public health, and preventing injury and damage to plants and animals. Subsequently, PD 1586 establishes an environmental impact statement system (EISS) in the country, including other environmental management-related measures.

The third period 1987-1996 highlights jurisdictional disputes among regulators in Laguna de Bay. One such case is the 1994 legal case of LLDA versus the Caloocan

LGU, wherein the City of Caloocan contested LLDA's issuance of an open dumpsite located in Camarin, Caloocan City for violation of anti-pollution policies. The City of Caloocan claimed it is within its power and jurisdiction as an LGU to maintain and operate the said dumping site, citing provisions of the Local Government Code of 1991 (RA 7160). However, the Supreme Court favored LLDA, explaining that LLDA's issuance of CDO to that dumpsite is a proper exercise of LLDA's power and authority under its charter and amendatory laws (Ynares & Torres, 2006).

As lake users and polluters increased over time, the DENR issued the Revised Effluent Regulations of 1990 (DENR Administrative Order [DAO] No. 35, s. 1990), which applies to all industrial and municipal wastewater effluents, to prevent, abate, and control industrial pollution nationwide. The salient feature of this policy is the new water quality parameters and their corresponding numerical limits, such as the biochemical oxygen demand (BOD). The BOD measures the approximate quantity of dissolved oxygen required by bacteria to stabilize organic matter in wastewater or surface water. It is also a standard test to assess wastewater strength.

In 1997-2006, stricter tools were employed by regulators to enhance implementation of laws and policies. For instance, the DENR's Ecowatch System (DAO No. 51, s. 1998) was adopted by the LLDA through its Board Resolution No. 104, s. 1999. The Ecowatch System is an approach to promote industrial compliance and encourage pollution reduction through public pressure. Under this policy, all industrial dischargers are required to have self-monitoring procedures, to be compliant with environmental standards, and to develop internal environmental management systems. The LLDA also approved the continuation of EUFS through Board Resolution No. 124, s. 1999. This is due to the success of EUFS in reducing BOD loadings in the lake in its early years of implementation. The LLDA also issued guidelines for installment payment of EUFS fees arrearages, the processing of LLDA Clearance applications, and the frequency of analysis and submission of self-monitoring reports (SMRs). Strict conditions and requirements for securing discharge permits were also specified and must comply with the National Effluent Quality Standards laid down in the DAO No. 35, s. 1990. In addition, LLDA issued Memorandum Circular [MC] No. 2000-5 for the compliance and monitoring protocol schedule of concerned firms/establishments operating within the Laguna de Bay Region. This policy requires a quarterly monitoring schedule of users according to their volumetric rate of discharge and the type of waste, attachment of compliance monitoring and inspection report form and wastewater sampling form as annexes in the reporting procedures.

As more livelihoods are established along the banks and vicinity of Laguna de Bay, the LLDA issued 2001 guidelines governing the operations of backyard/small-scale hog farms. LGUs, on the other hand, require sanitary permits and inventory of all hog farms in their jurisdictions. Hog farm operators must also secure sanitary, operation permits, and wastewater reduction mechanisms, i.e., biogas digester (Ynares & Torres, 2006). To further abate water pollution within the Laguna de Bay Region, the LLDA included all fastfood stores, restaurants, and similar establishments in issuing Board Resolution No. 191, s. 2003. This policy requires strict compliance with effluent standards and submission of SMRs aside from discharge permits and clearance certificates.

To address the perennial garbage problems in the country, the Ecological Solid Waste Management Act of 2000 (RA 9003) requires a nationwide systematic, comprehensive, and ecological solid waste management program that ensures the protection of the environment and public health through proper segregation, collection, transport, storage, treatment, and disposal of solid wastes. The Philippine Clean Water Act of 2004 (RA 9275) provides for comprehensive water quality management and applies to all water bodies in the country to control water pollution from land-based sources. These two major laws aim to strengthen previous pollution control and mitigation measures in the country.

In 2007-2016, more standards and guidelines of practice, NOVs, and CDOs were issued by regulators, particularly the LLDA and the DENR, to enhance laws and policies for environmental protection and mitigating pollution. The DENR issued new water quality guidelines and new general effluent standards (DAO 2016-08) for water bodies and discharge categories. The LLDA issued new guidelines for development projects, installations, and activities that extract water from Laguna de Bay and other water bodies the Laguna de Bay Region (MC No. 2016-01). LLDA's Environmental Regulatory Department-Surveillance Monitoring Division (ERD-SMD) issued 816 NOVs to industries for operating without discharge permits and for breach of effluent standards (LLDA, 2016).

The latter part of this period saw policies and tools adapting to sustainability and climate change resiliency and regulators' shifting gears of regulation, i.e., from purely regulatory bodies to a collaborative and developmental approach to regulating Laguna de Bay.

Table 1 presents the list of laws and policies employed to regulate wastewater discharge and effluent in the Laguna de Bay Region from 1966 to 2016.

Table 1
*List of Laws / Policies Regulating Wastewater Discharge /
Effluent in Laguna de Bay*

Year	Laws or Policies
1966-1976	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PD No. 984. <i>Providing for the Revision of Republic Act No. 3931 or the Pollution Control Law.</i> (1976). • PD No. 856. <i>Code on Sanitation of the Philippines.</i> (1975). • PD No. 1067. <i>Instituting a Water Code, Thereby Revising and Consolidating the Laws Governing the Ownership, Appropriation, Utilization, Exploitation, Development, Conservation and Protection of Water Resources.</i> (1976).
1977-1986	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PD No. 1151. <i>Philippine Environment Policy.</i> (1977). • PD No. 1152. <i>Philippine Environment Code.</i> (1977). • PD No. 1586. <i>Establishing an Environmental Impact Assessment System.</i> (1978). • <i>Effluent Regulations of 1978.</i> (1978). • PD No. 1096. <i>The Domestic Wastewater Disposal Policy of 1982.</i> (1982).
1987-1996	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DENR AO No. 34, s. 1990. <i>Revised Water Usage and Classification of Water Quality Criteria, Amending Sections No. 68 & 69, Chapter III of the 1978 NPCC Rules and Regulations.</i> (1990). • DENR AO No. 35, s. 1990. <i>Revised Effluent Regulations of 1990 Revising and Amending the Effluent Regulations of 1982.</i> (1990). • RA 6969. <i>Toxic Substances and Hazardous and Nuclear Wastes Act of 1990.</i> (1990). • DENR AO No. 26-92, s. 1992. <i>Amending Memorandum Circular No. 2, s. 1981: Appointment/Designation of Pollution Control Officers (PCO).</i> (1992).

- LLDA BR No. 7, s. 1993. *Approving New Schedule of Processing Fees for Environmental Permit/Clearance.* (1993).
 - Muntinlupa City Ordinance No. 93-112. *Approving the Wastewater Treatment Plant (Filtration Plant) in Barangay Putatan, Muntinlupa City, Metro Manila.* (1993).
 - Supreme Court G.R. 110120. *Issuance of Cease-and-Desist Order by LLDA to a Dumping Site in Caloocan City.* (16 March 1994).
 - LLDA BR No. 10, s. 1995. *Asserting the LLDA's Authority and Exclusive Jurisdiction in Laguna de Bay Concerning Issuance of Permits for Reclamation Projects, and Disallowing Any Non-Environmentally Feasible Activities at the Lake.* (1995).
 - LLDA BR No. 25, s. 1996. *Adoption of the Environmental Users Fee System and Approval of the Work and Financial Plan for its Operationalization in the Laguna de Bay Basin.* (1996).
 - LLDA BR No. 33, s. 1996. *Approving the Rules and Regulations Implementing the Environmental User Fee System in the Laguna de Bay Region.* (1996).
 - LLDA BR No. 24, s. 1996. *Adoption of the DAO No. 30, Section 3, Paragraph 3.3 (C) of DENR as part of the Policy of the LLDA.* (1996).
- 1997-2006
- LLDA BR. No. 41, s. 1997. *Adoption of the Definition of Development Activities per DENR Administrative Order No. 96-37 and Integration of Said Definition in the LLDA Rules and Regulations.* (1997).
 - LLDA BR No. 42, s. 1997. *Approving the Administrative Fines for Violations of the Rules and Regulations of LLDA.* (1997).
 - R.A. 9275. *Philippine Clean Water Act of 2004.* (2004).
 - LLDA MC No. 2, s. 1997. *Inspection and Investigation of Establishment's Compliance to Environmental Quality Standards and Pollution Control Rules and Regulations.* (1997).
 - LLDA BR No. 64, s. 1997. *Prescribing New Schedule of Processing Fees and Other Fees for Environmental Permits/Clearances Within the Laguna de Bay Region.* (1997.)
 - LLDA MC No. 99-05, s. 1999. *Inclusion of Total Coliform in the Parameters Being Monitored by the Authority.* (1999).
 - LLDA BR No. 104, s. 1999. *Adoption of DENR Administrative Order No. 51, s. 1998, pertaining to the Industrial Ecowatch System and Its Implementing Guidelines as Part of the Policy of LLDA.* (1999).
 - MC No. 99-02. *Amendment of Certain Provisions of Memorandum Order No. 97-84, s. 1997, Concerning the Simplified Requirements for Accrediting Pollution Control Officers.* (1999).
 - LLDA BR No. 105, s. 1999. *Approving the Policy Guidelines for the Installment Payment of Environmental User Fees (EUFs) Arrearages.* (1999).
 - LLDA Board Resolution No. 106, s. 1999. *Approving the Policy Guidelines Governing All Industrial Estates/Parks Within the Laguna de Bay Region.* (1999).
 - DENR AO No. 99-17, s. 1999. *Updating DAO No. 35, s. 1990, otherwise known as the Revised Effluent Regulations of 1990, Revising and Amending the Effluent Regulations of 1982.* (1999).
 - LLDA BR No. 124, s. 1999. *Approving the Continuance of the Environmental User Fee System as Regular Program of LLDA.* (1999).
 - LLDA MC No. 10, s. 2000. *Guidelines in the Frequency of Analysis and Submission of Self-Monitoring Report (SMR).* (2000).
 - LLDA MC No. 4, s. 2001. *Guidelines in the Processing of LLDA Clearance Application for Fast-Food Restaurants and Similar Establishments.* (2001).
 - LLDA MC No. 2002-5. *Compliance Monitoring Protocol and Schedule of Concerned Firms/Establishments Within the Laguna de Bay Region.* (2002).
 - DENR AO No. 30, s. 2003. *Implementing Rules and Regulations (IRR) for the Philippine Environmental Impact System (EIS).* (2003).
 - LLDA BR No. 191, s. 2003. *Approving the Policy Guidelines Governing All Fast Food Stores, Restaurants, and Similar Establishments within the Laguna de Bay Region.* (2003).
 - LLDA BR No. 234, s. 2004. *Adoption of Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA) System and its IRR.* (2004).

- DENR AO No. 61, s. 2004. *Delegation of Authority to the General Manager of the LLDA to Grant or Deny the Issuance of Environmental Compliance Certificate (ECC)/Certificate of Non-Coverage (CNC) for Project Located in Environmentally Critical Areas within the Laguna de Bay Region.* (2004).
 - LLDA MC No. 1, s. 2005. *Training Requirements for the Accreditation of Pollution Control Officers and Other Requirements.* (2005).
 - LLDA BR No. 298, s. 2006. *Amending Certain Provisions of the Rules and Regulations Implementing the Environmental User Fee System in the Laguna de Bay Region.* (2006).
- 2007-2016
- LLDA BR No. 2007-338. *Declaring the Establishment and Operationalization of Water Permitting, Registration and Monitoring System for the Extraction of the Lake Water of Laguna de Bay and Other Bodies of Water within the Laguna de Bay.* (2007).
 - EMB MC No. 2, s. 2009. *Amending Revised Procedural Manual for DAO 03-30 dated 30 June 2003 on the Classification of the Fast-food Stores, Restaurants and Similar Quick-Service Establishments.* (2009).
 - LLDA BR No. 440, s. 2013. *Equitable Sharing of Regulatory Fees Between Quezon City and LLDA.* (2013).
 - DENR AO No. 2016-08. *New General Effluent Standards (GES) and Water Quality Guidelines (WQG).* (2016).
 - NWRB BR No. 02-0108. *Transfer to LLDA the Surface Water Permitting Function within the Laguna de Bay Region.* (2008).
 - *Memorandum of Agreement of 2016 between LLDA and Non-LISCOP LGUs Supporting the Implementation of the Ecological Solid Waste Management Act of 2000.*
 - MMDA Resolution No. 14-1. *Mandating the LGUs of Metropolitan Manila to Enact / Revise City and Municipal Ordinances for Solid Waste Management.*
 - LLDA MC No. 2016-01. *Addendum to the Implementing Rules and Regulations Implementing Board Resolution No. 2007-388 for Water Permitting, Registration and Monitoring Systems.* (2016). (Applies to all development projects, installations, and activities that extract water from Laguna de Bay and other water bodies within the region)

Note. Originally compiled by the author based on various sources.

Multi-Institutional Regulatory Landscape

The study finds a multi-institutional regulatory landscape in the Laguna de Bay despite the presence of a primary regulator, i.e., the LLDA. The creation of LLDA stemmed from the problems and issues afflicting the lake in the 1960s, such as water pollution and decline in fishery production, that were hampering the lake's economic potential. Prompted by such problems, and to facilitate the rational utilization of Laguna de Bay's resources, policymakers passed into law RA 4850 in 1966, creating LLDA. This law granted the LLDA exclusive jurisdiction over the entire Laguna de Bay Region with regulatory and proprietary functions to manage and control the region's resources.

In 1975, PD 813 amended certain sections of RA 4850 and enlarged the mandate of the LLDA to address environmental protection, including the power to issue permits for the use of lake waters and any project or activity affecting the lake (LLDA, 2010). In October 1983, Executive Order (EO) No. 927 granted LLDA water rights over Laguna de Bay and other bodies of water within the region to effectively regulate and monitor activities, such as navigation, construction, and operation of fish pens. The LLDA is empowered to issue permits and clearances and to collect fees for using lake waters and its tributaries for beneficial purposes. EO 927 also introduced the term "Laguna de Bay Region," referring to the provinces of Rizal and Laguna; the cities of San Pablo, Pasay, Caloocan, Quezon, Manila, and Tagaytay; the towns of Tanauan, Sto. Tomas, and Malvar in Batangas province; the towns of Silang and

Carmona in Cavite province, the town of Lucban in Quezon province; and the cities and towns of Marikina, Pasig, Taguig, Muntinlupa, and Pateros in Metro Manila. The LLDA's jurisdiction refers both to its geographical jurisdiction, covering Laguna de Bay and its 2,920 km² watershed, and its administrative jurisdiction, that is, the Laguna de Bay Region—comprising the NCR, five provinces, 51 municipalities, and ten cities, totaling 66 LGUs with an area of 3,880 km² (Santos-Borja & Nepomuceno, 2005). The LLDA is a self-sustaining organization and does not receive a regular budget from the national government. It generates its operational costs and revenues from four major sources, namely: (a) resource user's fees, e.g., fishpen and fish cage fees and discharge permit fees; (b) regulatory fees, e.g., LLDA clearance; (c) service fees, e.g., surveys, delineation and mapping of aquaculture areas; and (d) overseas development assistance, e.g., foreign grants and donations (Santos-Borja, 2023).

Although LLDA has exclusive jurisdiction over Laguna de Bay Region, other entities, such as LGUs and other government agencies, also exercise their respective mandates, roles, and functions in the management of the lake. They are the "other regulators" and act as policymakers, developmental planners, or participants in infrastructures, projects, and programs. Their mandates, functions, and roles or involvement in Laguna de Bay are discussed briefly in the succeeding paragraphs.

The Local Government Code of 1991 devolved to LGUs the administration of basic services, such as agriculture, health, social welfare, maintenance of public works and highways, and environmental protection. LGUs with jurisdictions over Laguna de Bay also enact resolutions and ordinances to protect the lake from pollution and further degradation. In 2013, LLDA issued Board Resolution No. 439, s. 2013, mandating LGUs in the Laguna de Bay Region to require developers of housing and subdivisions in their jurisdictions to secure clearance and discharge permits as part of the application for building and business permits. This law also requires LGUs to compel developers to ensure an appropriate central sewerage system, implement a seepage management program, and provide land/road/right of way/access for sewerage facilities.

The Philippine Clean Water Act of 2004 (RA 9275) provides stiffer penalties for pollution violations to help improve the quality of all water bodies. It provides a comprehensive water pollution management program focused on pollution prevention. Under this policy, LGUs are required to implement a sewerage and seepage management system in their jurisdictions. LGUs must also ensure that all residential (including private subdivisions), commercial, industrial, institutional, and governmental establishments have proper sewage treatment and seepage management systems so that no wastewater shall be discharged to waterways without sufficient treatment. Also, septic tank owners and users must de-sludge at least once every five years or if the septic tank is filled with sludge.

By virtue of Executive Order 192, s. 1987, the DENR is primarily responsible for the conservation, management, development, and proper use of the Philippines' environment and natural resources, specifically forest and grazing lands, mineral resources, including those in reservation and watershed areas, and public lands. The LLDA adopts some of DENR's policies in regulating resources in Laguna de Bay. The Department of Agriculture (DA) is primarily tasked to improve farm income and generate opportunities for farmers, fishermen, and other rural workers including fishers in Laguna de Bay. The Department of Energy (DOE) cooperates with LLDA

in harnessing energy from the Laguna de Bay Region, for instance, in building hydropower plants to generate electricity. In 2008, the surface water permitting function of the National Water Resources Board (NWRB) in the Laguna de Bay Region was transferred to LLDA through the NWRB BR 02-0108.

Meanwhile, the National Housing Authority (NHA) was mandated by PD 757 to develop and implement a comprehensive and integrated housing program in the country, including housing development and resettlement, financing schemes, and delineation of government and private sector participation. The *Bagong Bahay*, *Bagong Buhay* (New House, New Life) housing project of the local government of Calamba City in Laguna province included the informal settlers living along the shorelines of Laguna de Bay, in coordination with the NHA's socialized housing scheme. The Housing and Land Use Regulatory Board (HLURB) assists LLDA in zoning and land use in the shorelands of Laguna de Bay.

Although these regulators aim to protect and develop Laguna de Bay, jurisdictional overlaps and disputes sometimes arise among them. For instance, in 2015, the Department of Public Works and Highways (DPWH) figured in a dispute with 300 local fishermen in Taguig City. These fishermen opposed the construction of the Laguna Lakeshore Expressway Dike (LLED) due to the possible loss of their fishing grounds (Mangunay, 2015).

Table 2 summarizes the multi-institutional regulators' roles or functions in Laguna de Bay Region.

Table 2
Multi-Institutional Regulators' Role/Function in Regulating Laguna de Bay

Regulator	Role/Function
Bureau of Fisheries and Aquatic Resources	Policies cover commercial/deep fishing outside LGUs' district; coordinates with LGUs in terms of fishery/aquaculture industry
Department of Agriculture	Provides policy framework to improve farm income, e.g., promotion of agricultural development
Department of Environment and Natural Resources	Primarily responsible for conservation, management and development of the country's environment and natural resources, including those in the Laguna de Bay Region; granted to LLDA in 2004, the authority to issue or deny environmental clearances to critical areas in Laguna de Bay, but reverted to DENR in 2007
Department of Energy	Cooperates with LLDA in harnessing energy from the lake, e.g., hydropower plants to generate electricity
Department of Public Works and Highways	Led the construction of the Napindan Hydraulic Control Structure project and the Lakeshore Expressway Dike (LLED); figured in conflicts with fishery sectors and affected communities due to these projects
Housing and Land Use Regulatory Board	Formulates and enforces policies on land use and provides technical assistance to LGUs in comprehensive land use plans; helps LLDA in matters of zoning and land use, particularly on shoreland areas at Laguna de Bay
Local government units	Territorial jurisdiction over overfishing and liquid and solid waste management in their localities

Laguna Lake Development Authority	Exclusive jurisdiction over Laguna de Bay with regulatory and developmental functions
National Housing Authority	Engages in housing projects for marginalized informal settlers occupying shoreland areas at Laguna de Bay in cooperation with LGUs concerned and other government agencies, e.g., the <i>Bagong Bahay</i> , <i>Bagong Buhay</i> housing project of Calamba City, Laguna
National Water Resources Board	Its water permitting functions over Laguna de Bay was transferred to LLDA through NWRB BR 02-0108, which also provided training for LLDA personnel on systems and procedures for regulating water use

Note. Originally compiled by the author based on various sources.

Issues, Challenges, and Lessons of Regulation

Major issues and challenges of regulating wastewater discharge and effluent in Laguna de Bay from 1966 to 2016 ranged from limitations of laws/policies and tools, jurisdictional disputes and overlaps among multi-institutional regulators, and inadequate resources of regulators among others.

Limitations of Laws, Policies, and Tools

Although LLDA's EUFS is one significant tool to control effluent loadings in Laguna de Bay, it also had limitations and controversies. For instance, water samples are diluted to lessen BOD loading concentration to avoid consequences of EUFS violations or non-compliance (Santos-Borja & Nepomuceno, 2005). The LLDA's continued issuance of CDOs and notices of anti-pollution violations to businesses and industries polluting the lake is deemed by the author as reflection of limitation of EUFS as it failed to harness total compliance of rules and regulations by the lake users. Another flaw of EUFS is in designating pollution control officers by businesses/industries who may submit tampered water samples and self-monitoring reports to cover up their companies' violations to avoid sanctions or penalties.

Burdensome Requirements in Permit Application

Regulatory tools changed over time. In the 1970s and 1980s, tools were few and simple. In the 1990s and 2000s, tools became more complex in forms and approaches as lake uses and users increased over time. For instance, a discharge permit then only required an application form and certain fees. Additional requirements now include LLDA clearance and evaluation, submission of water sources, consumption and wastewater generation and treatment, ECCs, EUFS fees, SMRs, designation of pollution control officers (PCOs), among others. For some users, these additional requirements are burdensome, leading to non-compliance or violation.

Costly Penalties for Violations

LLDA's anti-pollution policies carry costly penalty fees for violation and non-compliance. For instance, the LLDA increased the amount of penalty fee for failing to install own water treatment facilities from PHP1,000 pesos to PHP10,000 per day (Board Resolution 404, s. 2011). According to LLDA, this measure aims to compel concerned lake users to reduce their discharge of heavy metals and other pollutants

into Laguna de Bay (LLDA, 2011). However, the high cost of penalties is not a total deterrent for polluters in Laguna de Bay. In 2011 and 2013, the LLDA docketed 421 cases of violations and non-compliance of anti-pollution laws and policies and issued CDOs to businesses and industries for continuous discharging of wastewater in the lake's tributaries (LLDA, 2011, 2013). The LLDA also filed charges against 163 companies (out of 5,882 companies monitored) for violation of water pollution policies.

Regulators' Limitations

Ironically, the LLDA as the primary regulator does not receive a regular budget from the national government considering the magnitude of its mandate. The LLDA depends on its initiative to source funds to finance its operations, projects, and programs. As mentioned earlier, the LLDA generates revenues from issuing permits, clearances, and penalty fees, but these are insufficient to effect and support an effective and efficient regulation in the lake. LLDA's lack of police power and inadequate personnel to monitor polluters and violators are also contributing factors. The LLDA has only 20 personnel/staff to monitor around 10,000 businesses in the Laguna de Bay Region. Meanwhile, the LGUs are dependent on internal revenue allotment (IRA). In most cases, the IRA cannot fund operations, projects, and programs for the LGUs' constituents. Some ordinances issued by the LGUs failed to meet their goals due to the lack of funding to sustain policy implementation. The frequent change in leadership also compromised the LGUs' regulation of wastewater discharge/effluent in Laguna de Bay. Differing policy implementation among regulators also impedes effective regulation. This is illustrated when business permits are issued first by LGUs before issuing LLDA's or DENR's discharge permits which should be the other way around.

LLDA's Shifting Gear of Regulation

In the early 1970s, the LLDA propelled the fish culture in Laguna de Bay as part of its mandate to develop the lake's economic potential. However, when aquaculture became commercially viable, it contributed to overfishing and equity conflicts among other lake users. The LLDA then shifted its gear of regulation and positioned itself as the regulatory body. Similarly, the LLDA has a conflicting role and function because as the protector of the lake, it is at the same time an authority to issue discharge permits to lake users or polluters, e.g., businesses/industries operating in Laguna de Bay.

Regulators' Jurisdictional Overlaps and Disputes

Although regulators aim to protect the Laguna de Bay and its ecosystem from pollution, instances of jurisdictional overlaps and disputes among them emerged. As mentioned earlier, LLDA and the local government of Calocan City figured in a legal case that reached the Supreme Court. In this case, a local government unit legally challenged the exclusive jurisdiction of LLDA over the Laguna de Bay Region (G.R. No. 110120, 16 March 1994). In the end, the Supreme Court's verdict favored LLDA's jurisdictional rights.

Regulators' Best Practices as Lessons of Regulation

Learning from its past mistakes and to address the challenges of climate change, regulators try to invest in upgrading their regulatory policies and strategies. LLDA's 2016-2026 Laguna de Bay Updated Master Plan (UMP) focuses on climate change impacts by gearing policies towards disaster risk reduction and by harmonizing the four environmental laws namely, Clean Air Act, Clean Water Act, National Solid Waste Management Act, and the Fisheries Act. The plan also identified key issues that need immediate intervention, such as overcrowding of fish pens, illegal reclamation, industrial pollution, domestic sewage, the proliferation of water hyacinth, and sedimentation in Laguna de Bay.

In the new institutional re-engineering model stated in *Laguna de Bay Basin Master Plan for 2016 and Beyond: Towards Climate Resilience and Sustainable Development*, the LLDA plans to segregate its regulatory functions from its development mandates. It also aims to pursue infrastructure development projects through the private-public partnerships (PPP) modality, either in establishing a wholly owned subsidiary called the Laguna de Bay Development Corporation (LBDC), or in direct joint-venture arrangement with private sectors. In 2018, the LLDA general manager expressed his intention of changing the old mindset of LLDA that functions as strictly regulatory to a new mindset of a regulatory-developmental agency (Reyes-Aguila, 2018). To date, the LLDA has started prioritizing programs and initiatives to bring back Laguna de Bay to its healthy state, while providing livelihoods and protecting the rights of small fishermen. The LLDA also pushes for more partnerships with local and foreign entities to finance its projects and programs. Recently, the LLDA has partnered with Hungarian Water Technology Corporation to help rehabilitate Laguna de Bay (Lakewatch, 2018).

LGUs are investing more in waste composting and water treatment facilities in their jurisdictions. For instance, in Angono, Rizal, the installation of integrated solid waste management sub-project helps recover reusable and recyclable materials from collected solid wastes (Municipality of Angono, 2016). It also provides livelihood to the people through material recovery facilities (MRFs). The city of Muntinlupa recently inaugurated its public market wastewater treatment facility (Villanueva, 2005), and the municipality of Sta. Cruz, Laguna introduced the decentralized wastewater treatment system (DEWATS) to be used in slaughterhouse facilities (Abino, 2011).

Table 3
*Summary of Regulation of Wastewater Discharge /
 Effluent in Laguna de Bay in the Last Five Decades*

Period	Laws/Policies /Tools	Regulators	Issues/Challenges and Lessons
1966-1976	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Controlling/mitigating water pollution by institutionalizing laws and policies that are command-and-control in nature and approach •Laws/policies and tools are few and simple 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •LLDA as the primary regulator mandated by Republic Act 4850 •Other government agencies and LGUs also exercise their respective mandates and functions over Laguna de Bay •Employed traditional command and control regulation •Major decisions emanate from LLDA's Board of Directors 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Traditional command-and-control laws/policies •Rapid population growth •Urbanization •Industrialization •Resource extraction •Environmental degradation
1977-1986	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Strengthening laws/policies and tools through amendments, standards, codes of practice, guidelines, etc. •Flaws, loopholes of tools 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •LLDA's exclusive jurisdiction over Laguna de Bay and its region •LLDA's shifting gears of regulation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •More violations and non-compliance of laws/policies •Stiff penalties for violations •Costly fees for permits, clearances, penalties •Anti-pollution policies are not prioritized by some LGUs
1987-1996	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Emergence of jurisdictional disputes/conflicts among regulators and stakeholders •Reinforcing pollution control policies as lake users and polluters increased •Expensive fees for permits, certificates, penalties, etc. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •LLDA's jurisdictional conflicts with LGUs as other regulators •LLDA's limitations as regulator •LGU's limitations as regulator 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Limitation of tools, e.g., EUFFS, costly penalty fees, etc. •Inadequate resources of regulators, e.g., funds, personnel, technology •Change in policies as leadership change in some LGUs •Shifting gear of regulation among regulators
1997-2006	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •More and stricter tools are employed to implement and enforce laws/policies 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •LLDA's dominance as regulator •LGUs' jurisdictional rights and regulatory powers granted by Local Government Code of 1991 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Lack of police power of regulators •Weak monitoring and surveillance •Lack of fund, personnel, and modern technology of regulators

2007-2016	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Adapting laws/policies and tools for sustainability and climate change 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •LLDA's participative approach of regulation, e.g., co-management/ arrangement with LGUs and other stakeholders •LLDA's goal of regulation from regulatory body to developmental agency •Fostering cooperation and co-management with other regulators and stakeholders •Harnessing and strengthening public-private partnerships •Adapting best practices as good regulatory strategies 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Reinforcing laws/policies and tools for effective implementation and enforcement •Using a more collaborative and participative approach of regulation •Adapting laws/policies and tools for sustainable development, innovation, and change •Crafting laws and policies as proactive rather than reactive •Regulation geared for climate change resiliency
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Note. Created by the author based on various sources.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The study finds that laws and policies from 1966 to 2016 were instituted to control water pollution in the country and to preserve Laguna de Bay and other bodies of water from environmental degradation. Laws and policies adopt the command-and-control approach, imposing strict sanctions and costly penalties for violators. Laws, policies, and tools evolved in their aims, from controlling water pollution in the 1970s to 1980s, to water quality preservation and solid waste management in the 1990s, and the preservation and sustainability of the lake and its ecosystem in 2000s. Flaws and limitations were also observed in some policies and tools.

The study also finds a multi-institutional regulatory landscape in Laguna de Bay. The LLDA is not the sole authority in regulating activities in the lake, but the presence of LGUs and other government agencies complicates regulation. The LLDA, LGUs, and other government agencies' functions and roles sometimes overlap, creating confusion and jurisdictional disputes among them. Regulators' top-down decision-making approach has less leeway for stakeholders to participate in policymaking. Furthermore, regulators' inadequacies in funds, personnel, and modern technologies limit their capacities to implement and enforce effective regulation. From these findings, the study concludes that the weak or inadequate regulation of wastewater discharge and effluents in Laguna de Bay may have contributed to the continued deterioration of the lake's water quality.

The study therefore recommends a multi-pronged approach in regulating wastewater discharge and effluent in Laguna de Bay region. First, laws and policies must be regularly reviewed for these policies to adapt to the changing regulatory environment. Tools must be routinely assessed. Outdated and redundant tools must be recalibrated when needed. For instance, the LLDA clearance and environmental clearance certificate can be consolidated into one requirement for the application of a discharge permit. Sanctions, penalties, and fees must also be reformed, reduced, or consolidated to encourage compliance. Tools must be proactively crafted to adapt to the complexities and the changing regulatory landscape in the Laguna de Bay Region.

Second, regulators should foster a more collaborative and participative approach. The multi-institutional regulatory landscape in the lake may be harnessed in terms of co-management and cooperation. Combining the resources and expertise of various regulators can enhance policy implementation and achieve regulatory goals. Also, regulators' best practices must be added to the equation. For instance, the LGUs' solid and liquid waste disposal facilities must be emulated and promoted to other parts of the country. Tapping more public-private partnerships can generate more resources. Data sharing among regulators can also facilitate systems processing, for instance, in processing applications for permits and clearances.

Third, administering reforms in policy or decision-making processes may also help the policies respond to the challenges in the region. Combining top-down and bottom-up approaches can encourage collaboration and creativity among stakeholders and allow them to cultivate a sense of ownership and inclusivity. Businesses and industries operating in the lake region can help formulate specific policies catering to their needs and aspirations. Regular meetings and consultations with regulators and other stakeholders must be conducted to provide more avenues of interaction among them.

Fourth, red tape in transactions may be reduced using information communication technology (ICT) and digitalization for permit application, requirement submissions, payments, and other transactions. Although the LLDA and high-income LGUs already use ICT tools in their operations, low-income LGUs still need to level up their ICT applications to speed up business transactions. Finally, regulators must strengthen their capacities for resource generation and utilization.

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